

Thermal Degradation of *p*-Anisic Acid-Formaldehyde Condensation Product

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Manuscript received 20 November 1981, revised 11 June 1982, accepted 21 July 1982

p-Anisic acid has been condensed with formaldehyde and the thermal properties of the resin obtained have been studied by differential thermal analysis (DTA), and thermogravimetry (TG). Kinetics parameters for the decomposition reaction have been determined by different methods.

A survey of literature¹⁻⁴ reveals that products resulting from the condensation of benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acid with formaldehyde are industrially important. The present paper describes an attempt to study the thermal behaviour of such a condensation product using thermogravimetry (TG) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) techniques.

Experimental

Preparation of *p*-anisic acid-formaldehyde condensation product: *p*-Anisic acid (15.2 g), paraformaldehyde (3.0 g), glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and conc. sulfuric acid (1.0 ml) were mixed and heated at 120° for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into cold distilled water. The solid was dried in vacuum at room temperature.

The Linsesis thermo-balance for thermogravimetry and a micro cell⁵ for differential thermal analysis were used for the kinetics of decomposition using 25 or 50 mg of the resin for TG and 3 mg of the resin mixed with aluminium oxide for DTA studies at different heating rates in static air.

Results and Discussion

The condensation product did not soften at 240°. It started to decompose at higher temperature. The kinetics parameters were obtained using Chatterjee⁶ (Table 1a), Anderson-Freeman⁷, Broido⁸ and Flynn and Wall⁹ methods from the TG-study (Table 1b) and using Reich¹⁰ and Kissinger¹¹ method from DTA (Table 2). When the samples were heated at different rates (R. H.) for the TG study, the degradation occurred in two stages (Fig. 1). Major decomposition (60%) took place in the second step. The decomposition started at ~245° and ended at ~600°. The activation energy, E_A , obtained from the TG-study using the Chatterjee method for the first and the second stage of decomposition respectively ranged from ~15 to ~26 Kcal mol⁻¹. The decomposition followed a first order kinetics for both steps. The starting temperature of decomposition increased with increasing heating rate

TABLE 1a—KINETICS PARAMETERS (TG)

R.H. (°C min ⁻¹)	Amount mg	Decomposition temp. °C	ΔT °C	Weight loss %	Chatterjee method E_A (Kcal mol ⁻¹)	Order of reaction <i>n</i>
1.0	50	245-300	325	40	20.0	0.8
		300-570		60	25.5	1.1
	25	245-300	325	40	19.5	0.8
		300-570		60	25.0	1.1
2.5	50	260-320	320	40	18.0	1.0
		320-580		60	24.8	1.1
	25	260-320	320	40	18.3	1.0
		320-580		60	25.0	1.1
4.0	50	270-335	320	40	16.5	0.9
		335-590		60	24.0	1.0
	25	270-335	320	40	16.8	0.9
		335-590		60	23.5	1.0
6.5	50	290-340	310	40	15.0	1.3
		340-600		60	20.2	1.1
	25	290-340	310	40	15.3	1.3
		340-600		60	20.5	1.1

TABLE 1b—KINETICS PARAMETERS (TG)

R.H. (°C min ⁻¹)	Amount mg	Energy of activation E_A (Kcal mol ⁻¹)			Order of reaction <i>n</i>	
		Broido method	Flynn-Wall method	Anderson-Freeman method	Broido method	Anderson-Freeman method
1.0	50	18.1	33.1	29.5	1.0	0.8
	25	18.9	27.5	31.5	1.0	0.8
2.5	50	15.5		26.3	1.0	0.9
	25	15.9		27.8	1.0	1.0
4.0	50	14.8		25.1	1.0	0.9
	25	14.3		25.5	1.0	1.1
6.5	50	12.9		21.8	1.0	0.8
	25	13.5		22.6	1.0	1.3

TABLE 2—KINETICS PARAMETERS (DTA)

R.H. (°C min ⁻¹)	Peak temperature (°C)	Energy of activation, E_A (Kcal mol ⁻¹)		Order of reaction <i>n</i>	
		Reich method	Kissinger method	Reich method	Kissinger method
1.0	480	43.0	37.8	1.3	0.8
2.5	490	38.1		1.2	0.9
4.0	495	35.5		1.0	1.1
6.5	505	30.1		1.2	0.9

(Table 1a). The Anderson-Freeman method gave an E_A in the range of ~22 to ~32 Kcal mol⁻¹.

Fig. 2. DTA

TG and DTA curves of *p*-anisic-formaldehyde condensate product at various heating rate (R.H.).
 1—6.5°/min 2—4.0°/min
 3—2.5°/min 4—1.0°/min

That obtained from the Broido method varied from ~13 to ~19 Kcal mole⁻¹. The Flynn and Wall method gave a slightly higher E_a value compared to the other methods. In general, the decomposition followed first order kinetics.

The thermal parameters resulting from the DTA study using the method of Reich and Kissinger are given in Table 2. The degradation is exothermic

(Fig. 2). The temperature for the peak maxima varied from ~480 to ~505° for different R. H. The activation energy obtained employing the Reich method varied from ~30 to ~43 Kcal mol⁻¹ with the decreasing R.H. The Kissinger method yielded an E_a value of ~38 Kcal mol⁻¹. This value represents the overall degradation process. The evaluation of the data by this method involves many thermograms at different heating rates and assumes E_a to be the same for the degradation of the sample.

The E_a values from the DTA study are higher in comparison to those obtained from TG study. This could be ascribed to the retardation of decomposition of the polymer sample, which is sandwiched between neutral media in a narrow cavity of the DTA-micro cell, compared to the decomposition in a shallow boat of the TG sample holder.

The values of activation energy resulting from different methods are different, indicating that they depend on the heating rate and the method of calculation; different methods involving different limitations.

References

1. F. D. CHATTWAY and I. FARINHOLT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1737.
2. L. H. BOCK, U. S. 2284118 (1926), *Chem. Abs.*, 1942, 36, 62722.
3. S. K. CHATTERJEE, *J. Polym. Sci., A-1*, 1970, 8, 1299.
4. Fuji Photo Film Co. Ltd., Brit. 1 137580 (Cl. G. 03c) (1968); *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, 70, 82991f.
5. D. H. DESAI, C. K. PATEL, K. C. PATEL and R. D. PATEL, *Stärke*, 1972, 24, 43.
6. P. K. CHATTERJEE, *J. Polym. Sci., A-3*, 1965, 4253.
7. D. A. ANDERSON and E. S. FREEMAN, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1961, 54, 253h.
8. A. BROIDO, *J. Polym. Sci., A-2*, 1969, 1761.
9. J. H. FLYNN and L. A. WALL, *J. Polym. Sci., B-2*, 1966, 323.
10. L. REICH, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1969, 123, 42.
11. H. E. KISSINGER, *J. Res., Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1956, 57, 217h.